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PSYCHOLOGICAL VIOLENCE IN PAULA HAWKINS'S "THE GIRL ON THE TRAIN"

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Abstract

This research intends to depict traces of psychological violence in the novel *The Girl on the Train* by Paula Hawkins. The researchers investigate the Psychological Violence of Tom Watson on three females with his abusive language, immoral thoughts, and criminal actions. Moreover, it aims to describe the psychological torment endured by the female characters. Rachel battles depression and psychological setbacks, Megan's disappearance and subsequent murder remain mysterious, and Anna conceals Tom's infidelity in their marriage. This concept delves into Tom's psychological analysis, offering a deeper understanding of his character. The primary data source for this research is the text of the novel. The secondary data of this study is taken from books and articles from the internet. The narrative unfolds from the perspective of the Cognitive-Behavioral approach, providing unique insights into the character's mental states. It may help readers find a deeper meaning and a different interpretation of their reading. Furthermore, the researcher explores Rachel's memory loss, Tom's antisocial personality disorder, Anna's concern for her daughter's safety, and Tom's criminal activities, notably murder. Rachel lost everything due to her drinking habits and Tom's mental illness, leading to her decision to kill him out of fear for her own life. Hawkins portrays the life of a drunk, a divorcee, and an aimless lady. Therefore, the Novel revolves around all alcoholic side effects. Psychological Problems of different characters highlight Tom's Antisocial Personality Disorder in Cognitive Behavioral Theory.

Keywords: Violence, Alcohol, Murder, Antisocial, Personality, Disorder

Introduction

Psychological Violence in the form of mental abuse can cause emotional trauma to an individual. Psychological violence includes mental torture, abuse, and harm inflicted by loved ones or those close to us. The cause may be marital relationships, family, friends, and loved ones. Psychological violence can also be present in other forms of abuse, even when not directly apparent. This research explores emotional abuse, psychological violence, and mental torture experienced by characters in Paula Hawkins's novel *The Girl on the Train*. Using Cognitive-Behavioral Theory (CBT), this research examines how psychological violence can manifest as domination, oppression, and victimization, encompassing physical, psychological, sexual, spiritual, and emotional forms of abuse. In addition, it refers to any behavior that frightens, manipulates, threatens, hurts, disgraces, blames, harms, or wounds someone. Psychological violence can happen to anyone of any race, age, sexual orientation, religion, or gender. It can take place in a range of relationships, including couples who are married or living together. It affects people of all socio-economic backgrounds and education levels. This research explores the psychological disorders of characters, which the author excellently presents. The entire story leads readers to interpret the novel with different forms of violence. Regarding the causes and healing of psychological disorders, bitter past experiences can cause psychological issues for an individual (Febriani, 2018). At the same time, Khaleda (2017) argues that human needs advance individuals into the trap of psychological disorders. In addition, Kayani et al. (2019) argue that social degradation and humiliation can also lead individuals to violence. Besides, Tamara (2017) investigated in the context of psychological traumas where therapeutic sessions can improve patients' lives. However, the entire story leads readers to interpret and understand the novel with different forms of violence. Kayani and Hameed

(2021) discuss that socio-psychological elements may make violence unacceptable for individuals. Another study shows the recovery of traumas like "tension, excitement, hostility, suspiciousness, and anger control" (Trappler & Newville, 2007, p. 318). The studies (Briere, 2002; Finkelhor et al., 2013) also figure out the racial traumas: "65% of African American youth report traumatic experiences like physical and sexual abuse, witnessing domestic violence compared to 30% of their peers from other races" (Metzger et al., 2005, p. 12). The novel also deals with the complex phenomenon of a mysterious murder and murder for the sake of survival and self-defense. The text also explores the psychosexual relationships between the characters and their love relations with each other. Extramarital affairs may have many reasons that further show their characters' true nature and psychological role in the novel. Through this novel, the researcher exposes the psychological analysis and the violence regarding characters Rachel Watson, Tom Watson, Anna Watson, Scott Hipwell, and Megan Hipwell. Tom's ex-wife, Rachel, is a 32-year-old woman battling depression and alcohol addiction. It caused her psychologically disturbed person because of the physical torture and psychological and emotional violence from her ex-husband. She takes the same Train daily and pretends to go to her job but, due to over-drinking, is kicked out. She usually blackouts and does not remember actions that happened in the past. Tom left her due to her childlessness and her psychological and physical struggles. She was no more attractive to anyone because of her alcoholism. Anna, Tom's current wife, is perceived as stable and gave birth to their child, Evie. However, she is always irritated by Rachel when she sees her. Another major character is Megan, Tom's mistress, with whom Tom has a secret relationship while living with Anna. Tom is insincere, a liar, a murderer, a seducer, and morally corrupt. She

has experienced trauma due to her troubled past. In her present life, she is unhappy with Hipwell. She feels comfort in having relationships like her psychiatrist Kamal and Tom just for the pleasure of forgetting her past. Psychological violence caused her ultimate death. Tom killed Megan because he wanted her to remain his mistress and insisted on aborting the baby. When she refused, he brutally murdered her by repeatedly striking her head with a stone until she died, Tom is the lying, scheming, lethal adversary character of the book. Tom portrays himself as a caring spouse, making a valiant effort to earn a living wage for his family, yet Rachel and Anna find themselves close to the furthest limit of the novel. Tom's entire life—and persona are based on a delicate and upsetting snare of privileged insights and falsehoods. While Tom was hitched to Rachel, he made a propensity for depicting himself as a casualty of her intoxicated furies. As Rachel's drinking is filled with pity over her powerlessness to imagine a youngster, she starts spiraling wild. Tom discloses to Rachel many mornings that she had passed out obnoxiously or genuinely mishandled him. In any case, Tom ruthlessly mishandled Rachel, exploiting Rachel's failure to frame recollections while intoxicated. At the point when the original starts, Tom is as of now remarried to Anna, who was his love after Rachel. Initially, Anna and Tom hire Megan to care for Evie. Tom and Megan start an undertaking relationship, yet when Megan. Tom assaults Rachel and infers that he intends to kill her; Rachel kills him in self-preservation, utilizing a wine tool. Tom's untruths are uncovered, and Rachel can start fixing her recollections, her life, and her self-appreciation—all of which Tom deliberately looks to demolish. Tom is guileful, attractive, and beguiling—it is difficult to completely realize what persuades his brutal conduct throughout the story. Anna helps to kill Tom because of her aggression toward him for cheating and killing Megan (Hawkins, 2015).

Problem Statement

This research intends to depict traces of psychological violence in the novel *The Girl on the Train* by Paula Hawkins.

Research Questions

- a. How does psychological violence ruin Rachel's whole life?
- b. How are the mysterious causes of murders explored in the novel *The Girl on the Train*?

Research Objectives

- a. To explore the issues behind the psychological disorder of Rachel.
- b. To investigate the mysterious causes of murders in the novel.

Significance of the Study

The study deals with the psychological violence in the selected novel. It is significant because it explores the domestic violence of society that causes people to develop several psychological issues and problems. It is a need of the hour to counter them by highlighting awareness of such domestic elements. People are suffering from memory loss, mantle disorder, and stress. This study attempts to indicate such elements by analyzing Hawkins' novel *The Girl on the Train*.

Literature Review

The literature discusses "The influence of Rachel's motive to help Megan on her personality development as seen in *Hawkins's The Girl on the Train*" by Raisa Hani Tamara. The researcher sheds light on Rachel's motive to help Megan, which becomes a positive element of Rachel's personality. After seeking the help of a psychiatrist, she could recall a few moments related to Megan. The researcher is trying to tell us that Rachel's struggle with missing a girl was the actual step that made her personality better because, during this period, she was not consuming any alcohol (Tamara, 2017). The researcher explores Nadiyah Khaleda's "The Main Character's Hierarchy of Needs in *The Girl on the Train Novel*." Khaleda highlights the theme of safety and love according to Abraham

Maslow's hierarchy of human needs. Additionally, the researcher shows us that Rachel was mad about her love and physical needs. According to Khaleda, Rachel is desperate for her needs and fulfills her need for love from her friend Cathy. The researcher analyzed the main characters of *The Girl on the Train* in light of the hierarchy of needs (Khaleda, 2017). Fitria Febriani highlights "Megan's Trauma in Paula Hawkins' *The Girl on the Train*." The researcher highlights the reasons for Megan's Traumatic experiences descriptively. She aimed to analyze the psychological problems she faced related to her life, especially her past (Febriani, 2018). Megan's trauma is analyzed based on the symptoms of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD). The results show that Megan experiences PTSD symptoms such as insomnia, unbalanced emotions, and hypervigilance. Meanwhile, the way Megan deals with her trauma is shown by her decision to become a babysitter and to overcome her fear of vehicles. (Febriani, 2018) In addition, another research conducted on the novel is "The main characters' Motives of Murder reflected in Paula Hawkins' *The Girl on the Train*" by Vincentia Wika Carraciola at the University Sanata Dharma. The researcher analyzed the major female characters in the novel and the murder investigation of Megan Hipwell. Research is based on psychoanalysis: id, ego, and superego. It investigates that three females are suffering from depression due to Tom. The researcher highlights the different types of human behavior, and psychological disturbance becomes the reason for murder sometimes. According to this research, Rachel's id was dominant; she had an affair with Scott Hipwell because of her pleasure. Megan was a depressed lady and a seducer with painful memories. Anna was also high in id because she was selfish in her love with Tom. He was completely dependent on ID, which wanted to fulfill his needs at any cost. Due to this psychological disturbance, he

killed his mistress, Megan Hipwell (Carraciola, 2018).

Paiva (2015) investigates "Physical and psychological violence against the Elderly: Prevalence and associated factors" with the help of a survey and analysis. The study aims to analyze the percentage of victims suffering from violence. Researchers analyzed that these victims are mentally ill, some are hospitalized, and others could not do anything right due to their life partners. In addition, there is another research paper, "Violence against Women: Synthesis of Research for Practitioners" by Bonnie. E. Carlson (2000). The researcher investigates that violence against women is a legal and social problem, so different agencies are working on it for justice. Some physical wrong actions were the reaction of Mental illness or depression. Psychological violence is another form of violence associated with domestic problems. It is a risky problem that affects the mind badly, and Psychologists need to plan a proper treatment with the Cognitive Behavior Theory. They found 11 female Victims who were assaulted sexually, physically, and psychologically. According to another report, a Global systematic study of violence against women explored that almost 30% of women worldwide are victims of aggression by their partners. After much depression, there is a high risk of suicide attempts and drug addiction in Brazil, as cited in (Habigzang, 2108).

Research Gap

Previous studies (Carraciola, 2018; Febriani, 2018; Khaleda, 2017; Tamara, 2017) have been conducted on Patriarchal attitudes and social crises in society, psychological analysis, social struggle, human needs, personality Development, cultural Phenomena, and Motives of Murder. This study examines Psychological Violence with the help of Cognitive Behavioral Theory in Hawkins's *The Girl on the Train*. *The Girl on the Train* is the best sample of Psychological

Violence caused by the novel's antagonist, Tom Watson. In previous studies mentioned above, researchers investigated Megan's trauma, 'Rachel's drinking habit,' but this study exposes the psychological condition of Tom Watson, who was the reason for crime, violence, and murder. This study addresses a gap in the existing research by thoroughly examining the effects and causes of antisocial personality disorder within the context of psychological violence in *The Girl on the Train*.

Research Methodology

The study is qualitative and interpretive. The close reading method analysis has been adopted to interpret the text of the novel *The Girl on the Train*. Secondary sources are utilized from different journals articles, websites, and the internet.

Theoretical Framework

This section focuses on the analytical and descriptive study of Psychological Violence in Paula Hawkins's *The Girl on the Train*. This research conducts a qualitative analysis of the text and its characters by applying the theory of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy. The novel is categorized as a fiction book consisting of 316 pages. This novel is divided into a three-first-person narrator. The study further applies Aaron Beck's Cognitive-Behavioral Theory (2015) to analyze the novel and its themes. This approach to Psychological Violence and CBT Theory applies to the characters and the circumstances they face in the novel. The psychological approach is useful to analyze this study because it focuses on the work of literature. The researcher explores the major field of psychotherapy used to analyze the behavior of people with irrational beliefs or faulty Cognition. The abundance of irrationality may harm a person concerning psychological issues. It was developed for anxiety and depression and later extended to treat mental health disorders. Its primary goal is to understand the patient's psychological emotions, sudden outcomes, and distorted ideas.

Similarly, 'In Cognitive Theory: Basics and Beyond,' [Judy Beck \(2015\)](#) defines ten principles of Cognitive Behavioral Theory and Therapy:

- Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) is based on the developing formulation of the clients and their ever-evolving problems.
- It focuses on the cooperation of understanding in the session of the patient.
- It emphasizes the proper activation of a person.
- CBT relates to difficulties or problems with proper goals.
- CBT is based on a process that is a learning process about recovering a person from his faulty Cognition.
- CBT emphasizes fixed and limited time; they cannot take three-hour sessions.
- Their session is based on a compact structured system.
- It teaches the client to find out his irrational thoughts after remembering his past or previous wrong actions that used to make him criminal or depressed.
- CBT has different techniques that are used to make a person normal. It changes his thoughts, beliefs, and perceptions.

Further, this procedure is used to help patients. They identify their problems and then improve their negative and irrational thoughts healthily to make them a good person. It is a process of cooperation of both parties with sincerity; otherwise, it is difficult to fix thoughts well. [Beck \(2015\)](#) defines in his book *Cognitive Therapy of Personality Disorders* as a Cognitive Behavioral theory that can be used to treat people with a psychoanalytic Perspective. They used different models to identify the problems of patients. They turn their irrational thoughts into rational ones because they may harm society or their family. We do not need to go far because a prominent example of Tom in Hawkins's *The Girl on the Train* can be found. The research aims to identify his rubbish

thoughts, dysfunctional beliefs about Rachel, or family relations that make him fearless. CBT focuses on ego and egoistic thoughts that make a person daring, shrewd, and fearless. The Cognitive Process involves the Product of the Process, consisting of Cognitive and behavioral techniques used to help patients individually. Cognitive Behavioral Therapy is also used in Psychotherapy. Beck developed the Cognitive Behavioral approach for personality disorders. Cognitive Behavioral Therapy was developed to get rid of depression and damaged cognitions. Analysts and psychotherapists got more awareness from centers of Cognitive Therapy worldwide except in Antarctica. The book describes the concepts of different authors who have developed a cognitive Behavioral Theory to recognize personality disorders. During their initial analysis of the treatment of affective disorders, they identified "ego analysts" from the works of Adler, Horney, Sullivan, and Frankl (Beck, 2015). According to CBT, patients frequently present themselves as victims of human beings, but others are aware they sometimes become liars, criminals, aggressive, and rapists. Patients may lack concern for their behaviors and their impact on others. Cognitive Behavioral Theory has a different concept for each disorder according to its causes and effects. Another thing with a personality-disordered person is anticipating the depression aggravated by a therapeutic process that challenges their identity and thoughts.

Three elements of schema are helpful in the process of CBT.

Behavioral: Individuals with this type of disorder are analyzed through behavioral aspects.

Cognitive: It involves a process to analyze irrational thoughts in personality disorders.

Affective: This process explores cognitive therapy's effectiveness after analyzing patients' cognitive conceptualization.

There are a few Assumptions of Antisocial Personality Disorder extracted by this study:

- Individuals may exhibit symptoms of this disorder, referred to as 'conduct disorder' if it persists until age 15. However, if these behaviors persist beyond 18, it is diagnosed as antisocial personality disorder, indicating the continuity of socially threatening behaviors into adulthood.
- Antisocial Personality Disorder shows the criminal behavior of an individual. Cognitive Behavioral theory is used to change the behavior and thoughts of patients.
- A Psychotherapist analyzes the cognition and behavior of an individual.
- In terms of etiology, it involves the idea of the superego during treatment. If a person has a superego, then his treatment is less effective. An individual with Antisocial Personality disorder may be considered untreatable if they are unaccepted of society's rules and social norms.

Textual Analysis

This section looks at the Cognitive Behavioral Theory that deals with personality disorders, but the research explores antisocial personality disorder. This research also opens up the discussion regarding several layers of psychological Violence. Individuals with Antisocial Personality Disorder treat others cruelly or unkindly, which reminds the reader of the character of Tom Watson. Mostly, these types of people violate the norms of society, speak a lie, involve wrong actions, and use alcohol frequently. This research shows a few characters' psychological violence and mental condition concerning the disorders. Rachel's psychological disturbance is attributed to everyone around her; nobody understands her because she is an alcoholic due to her stressed and disarranged thoughts. For example, Hawkins (2015) portrays this situation: "My mother used to tell me that I had an overactive imagination; Tom said that too" (p. 11). Due to her excessive drinking and

fractured memories, she is the unreliable witness and narrator in the novel. In another section, she narrates herself;

"Let's be honest: Women are still only really valued for two things: their looks and role as mothers." Rachel laments that she feels worthless as a female after having many problems and losing her looks through drinking. However, Tom is responsible for everything, but she does not have bad feelings for him. Because she still loves him: "I remember now, I told him that I still loved him, that I always would, Please, Tom, Please, I need to talk to you. I miss you" (p. 22). Despite he is so rude to her, she still loves him. She expects a call back from him when he does not pick up phone calls, but he sends his messages angrily and impolitely. Furthermore, the novel presents Tom's psychological and physical torture to Rachel. She narrates, "He dropped me off. He took my hand. I thought it was a gesture of kindness, of assurance, but he squeezed tighter and tighter and tighter until I cried out; his face was red when he told me that he would kill me if I ever did anything to harm his daughter" (p. 108). Because of her childlessness, she loved her daughter, but it was unacceptable for Anna and Tom. He is shrewd and pretends sympathy for Rachel but hates her badly. He physically, mentally, and verbally tortured her with his wrong actions and words. He had used mostly abusive words for Rachel that made her psychologically disturbed. He was addicted to threatening her almost daily without any reason. "Every time I heard Tom's voice in my head, as clear as if he were right there, right next to me, his lips against my ear *_you were blind drunk. Filthy, stinking drunk _* and I jolted awake, shame washing over me like a wave" (p. 257). After getting divorced, he was still in her mind. She is a damaged drunk who spoils everything whenever she listens to his words. He always pretends that she is responsible for this divorce, but he is a

corrupt guy with a disordered personality who always violates the norms and rules of society. She describes her depressed condition: "I don't have words to describe what I felt that day, but now sitting on the train, I am furious, nails digging into my palms, tears stinging my eyes. I feel a flash of intense anger. I feel something has been taken away from me" (p. 38). Megan and Scott pretend to be a perfect couple, but they are so far from it. It was another violence that was making her worse and angry. She feels heartless and breathless after seeing Megan with Kamal, her psychiatrist, but she does not know. All his abusive habits and behavior show his antisocial personality disorder. Three females are victims of psychological and physical violence from Tom. Rachel was tired from anything from inside and outside. However, Rachel narrates love that "I have never understood how people can blithely disregard the damage they do by following their hearts. Who was it said that following your heart is a good thing? It is pure egotism, a selfishness to conquer all" (p. 39). She is purely disappointed by love because of Tom. All his abusive habits and behavior show his Antisocial Personality Disorder. When they lived together, he always blamed her for everything, even though he told her he got fired because of her, but was she such a great liar? I know Tom hates me and has turned against me: old colleagues, friends, even my mother. They look at me with disgust and contempt, and no one will listen to me; no one will let me tell them how sorry I am. I feel awful, desperately guilty; I can't think of what I have done. (p. 180) Rachel's blackout gave him confidence. She feels guilty; it is all about fake stories, but he tortured her physically and psychologically when he got the chance. Rachel says, "I was in the underpass, and he was coming towards me, one slap across the mouth and then his fist raised, keys in his hand, searing pain as the serrated metal smashed down against my skull" (p. 258).

Megan and Anna are both victims of violence, not only Rachel. After the murder of Megan, Rachel, and Anna face psychological violence from Tom, and then Anna feels sympathy for her: "The thought that she and I _ fat, sad Rachel and I _ are now in the same boat is unbearable" (p. 276). Furthermore, Rachel narrates in the novel that he is an astonishing liar and a fabulous story-maker. He used to behave like a victim injured by Rachel when she was drunk. Rachel believes her every single blame because she blackouts everything. "I try not to think of the worst days, but the memories crowd into my head at times like this" (p. 109). Tom's voice and words were with her every time. She recalls his harsh words, "I don't want to go anywhere with you anymore," he told me. 'You ask me why I never invite friends round, why I don't like going to the pub with you anymore; you honestly want to know why? It is because of you. Because I'm ashamed of you" (p. 109). However, the Avoidance of drinks makes Rachel thoughtful and normal. She can almost recall all those blackouts of the past that were blurred for Rachel. Tom Performs like a shrewd guy who claims she does not know what happens that day when she drinks. She makes up the most, but it is not the story. He is trying to blame Rachel for everything. Then he tried to make her quiet through his physical torture: "He Puts a hand on my shoulder, then runs his finger under my throat, applying just the slightest pressure. 'What am I going to do with you, Rach?" (p. 296) His abusive behavior was not only physical torture. It was his psychological violence, too. He is so sharp and keen that it makes her personality disordered the guy. Tom continually makes her confused, but Rachel recalls everything that happened that day when Megan was missing. He is trying to hide his criminal acts through his taunt. He blames her for his every wrong deed. He is trying to prove that she is a drunkard, so she is unreliable. Nevertheless, Rachel's memory

returns, and she tells his reality to Anna. Rachel exposed that he had an affair with Scott's wife, Megan Hipwell. In addition, he accepted his affair and murder unconsciously by saying, "That thing with Megan, it was just ... just a bit of fun" (p. 294). After getting to know the reality of Tom, Anna cries badly. Because it was all unexpected for her, like Rachel, he told them he loved them badly. Rachel ultimately proves to her that Tom murdered Megan, and then Tom comes home. There is a fight; Tom attacks Rachel, and Rachel kills Tom with a corkscrew in self-defense. An additional twist comes the politeness of Anna, who wants to make sure Tom is no more. Not because he is a murderer but because he lied to her. Tom psychologically and abusively tortured pregnant Megan. He narrates his mentally disordered actions: I was saying, I'm not interested in your baby, it's got nothing to do with me.' He shakes his head. 'She got all upset, but when Megan gets upset She's not like Rachel. There is no crying and whining. She was screaming at me, swearing, saying all sorts of shit, telling me she'd go straight to Anna, she wasn't going to be ignored, her child was not going to be neglected . . . Christ, she just wouldn't fucking shut up. So . . . I don't know; I just needed her to stop, so I picked up a rock. (p. 303). Rachel is a witness, so after Megan, he wants to kill Rachel, too. In anxiety, she elaborates, "I pitch myself forward and run. I enter the hallway – my hand is almost on the door handle when I feel the bottle hit the back of my skull. There's an explosion of pain, white before my eyes, and I crumple to my knees. His fingers twist into my hair as he grabs a fistful and pulls me back into the living room, where he lets go" (p. 305). However, Rachel and Anna finally kill Tom. Both loved him badly, but his psychological disturbance became the reason for his murder.

Conclusion

The research presented here underscores the psychological disturbances affecting the characters, especially the Protagonist, Rachel Watson, who suffers a lot and is distracted from social norms and networks. The entire novel describes the present era in which the use of technology is seen and the prevailing social and economic development of American society. Though time has developed, the role of the male is still dominant, which can be seen in the novel. How women suffered and the dilemma of society could haunt marital relationships is discussed. Rachel's ex-husband, Tom Watson, is the only reason for Psychological, sexual, verbal, and Physical violence against Rachel, Megan Hipwell, and Anna Watson. Rachel suffers a distressful and life-threatening battle with her circumstances. Through the character of Rachel, Hawkins throws the light on a male-dominant society where females are suppressed for their rights, love, and peaceful life. She travels on Pointless journeys just for the sake of Pleasure. Tom Watson's character represents a corrupt and mentally ill person who wants to fulfill his needs by hook or crook. Tom exploited and killed her just for his own needs. Upon analyzing the behavior and thoughts of all characters, Tom's behavior and all wrongdoings prove that he is an antisocial Personality-disordered guy with irregular thoughts and abusive behavior all the time. Even he used his smile just for the sake of need. Therefore, he has all the symptoms of an Antisocial Personality Disorder Person as we know he is Manipulative, sociopath, selfish, a liar, shrewd, a sinner, and a murderer. So, the Researcher exposed the character of Tom, who is involved in a Personality disorder and likes to violate the laws without any specific reason. While researching Tom's violating norms, Rachel's barren life is full of psychological and physical violence and mysterious murders.

Major Findings

The researcher investigates some basic findings that aim to highlight Psychological Violence in The Girl on The Train:

- Rachel usually blackouts due to over-drinking and cannot remember things that happened in the present and past. This flaw of her nature creates a great mess in her life.
- The major finding is that Tom's disloyalty towards every woman in his life turns his life over. He always lies to Rachel when she is drunk. He was in a relationship with Anna while living with Rachel, and after getting a divorce from Rachel, he cheated on Anna because of Megan. He did not want any child from Megan and killed her because of the fear of exposure.
- Anna is a selfish lady who likes to call the second woman who has a relationship with a married man, but psychological violence makes her worse. At the end of the novel, only Rachel, Anna, kills Tom because of his disloyalty and her daughter's better future. Everything was acceptable to her, but not his criminal Behavior or antisocial personality disorder.
- Megan was traumatized by the past. She always saw men as an object of her satisfaction. She also cheated on her husband. However, Tom mercilessly kills her; later, her absence and death create mystery in the novel. Furthermore, the researchers explore the psychological Pressure and Physical violence from Tom that become the reason for her death.
- Moreover, the whole novel presents the concept of Trains that symbolize the few major characters who see the train to escape their desires or want to forget their troubles.
- The current study further recommends indicating and analyzing other texts where the characters are the prey of psychological violence.

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